

Abstract Book

th **International
Horticulture**

Conference & Expo-2025

Horticultural Transformation: Sustainable Food Safety & Security

April 15-17, 2025

Emerging Viticulture Industry In Pakistan-An Overview Of Challenges and Prospects

Muhammad Hashir Khan (Department of Horticulture, PMAS-Arid Agriculture University Rawalpindi), Irfan Ali (Department of Horticulture, PMAS-Arid Agriculture University Rawalpindi), Muhammad Tahir Akram (Department of Horticulture, PMAS-Arid Agriculture University Rawalpindi), Rizwan Rafique (NFREC-IFAS, University of Florida USA 32351)

Corresponding email: arid132@uaar.edu.pk

Abstract

Pakistan has a very long-standing history in the cultivation of grapes, spanning several decades. Contrary to traditional viticulture regions across the globe, optimized grapes cultivation management strategy is still at a developing stage in Pakistan. Multifaceted challenges, in terms of climatic variability, high disease incidence, lack of a robust viticulture breeding programme, poor vineyard management, shortage of skilled labor, inappropriate postharvest handling, lack of storage facilities coupled with market volatility all come together to influence fruit production and net profitability from the vineyard. The objective of this review is to elucidate the current status, challenges and way forward for a profitable grapes cultivation in Pakistan. Traditionally, Balochistan is the main growing region with a chunk share of more than 90%, fertile plains of Punjab have shown a rapid rise with area crossing around 2000 ha. Grapes production in KPK have been varying with years and many new emerging groves show a high potential for these areas. Over the years, the traditional cultivars have faced a major decline and replaced by new early maturing cultivars such as King s Ruby, Flame Seedless, Perlette and Sultanina C particularly in Punjab and KPK areas. Similarly, areas in Kashmir and Gilgit Baltistan are suitable for commercial viticulture. Some traditional commercial grapes cultivation areas in Sindh have been lost due to climatic, lack of irrigation, disease and marketing issues. Amongst the others like lower production, inferior fruit quality coupled with excessive pesticide applications mark as key challenges to the industry. However, opportunities abound with increasing local interest in grape production and the possibility of economic profits through public private collaborations. Choosing a 3R approach i.e., right cultivar, right place and right management production technology, value addition-training and research and supply chain management through a public-private partnerships, could overcome many of the challenges faced by viticulture sector and turn it into multi-million industry in Pakistan.

Keywords: Emergence, Grapes, Practices, Production.